

D9.2 Project Website

Deliverable number	D9.2
Deliverable title	Project Website
Nature ¹	DEC
Dissemination Level ²	PU
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Official submission date:	31/10/2019
Actual submission date:	26/02/2020

¹ **R**=Document, report; **DEM**=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC**=website, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**=other

² **PU**=Public, **CO**=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), **CI**=Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

Modifications Index	
Date	Version
04/12/2019	0.1 First draft by Konstantinos Gkanetsos
05/12/2019	0.2 Corrections - editing Panagiotis Giannakopoulos
22/12/2019	0.3 Additions of updated screenshots
26/01/2020	0.4 Second draft version
27/1/2020	0.5 Comments by Sophia Adam
31/01/2020	0.6 Final draft by Panagiotis Giannakopoulos
16/02/2020	0.7 Final updated Version
17/2/2020	0.8 Comments by Sophia Adam
24/2/2020	0.9 Finalised document
25/02/2020	1.0 Final Review by Sophia Adam

This work is a part of the HYPERION project. HYPERION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 821054.

Content reflects only the authors' view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

ICCS	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems
IEMC	INTERCULTURAL EURO-MEDITERRANEAN CENTRE FOR UNESCO
PC	Program Coordinator
PMB	Project management board
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The aim of this deliverable is to provide a brief description of the developed HYPERION website and its main functionalities, which is the objective of the Task 9.3 Development and use of dissemination materials and tools under WP9, Dissemination, Communication and Standardization Activities.

Within WP9 all the activities linked to the communication and dissemination of the project outcomes and results are highly served by web-based means. Following this rationale, a project website has been developed in view of communicating and disseminating the project, including project objectives, project's news, technology news, all project public documents (deliverables, presentations, scientific publications etc.), as well as consortium contacts.

The HYPERION website url address is www.hyperion-project.eu emphasising the link to the European Union and adding value to the contribution of the project in the sustainability of historic areas. It promotes the vision and the mission of the HYPERION project and communicates the project developments and assets to its various and diverse target audiences.

The project's website has been designed and prepared by IEMC, thanks to the support of all partners. The website will be maintained and updated in a regular basis during the project's lifetime and for five years after the project's end in order to provide all interested stakeholders with information on project results and contact details.

Below are presented the computing infrastructure to host and run the website, as well as a detailed description of the structure and content of the HYPERION website. All pages and sub-pages that consist the website are presented in details and accompanied with screenshots.

1. PROJECT WEBSITE

1.1 Introduction

The HYPERION website (www.hyperion-project.eu) constitutes one of the main communication and dissemination channels of the project. It is the main visual interface for communicating the vision, the mission and the results of HYPERION to its targeted audiences as well as to the general public.

It has been online from the beginning of the project, on June 2019, initially as a landing page providing the main information concerning the project. The website's final version, which was launched at month eight (M8) from the project kick off meeting in Athens, follows the brand guidelines set in the beginning of the HYPERION project, as used in all project communication materials, in order to maintain the integrity of the HYPERION brand identity.

The website is dynamically adjusted to any operating system and all portable devices.

The website's official language is English.

The HYPERION website aims to be the backbone of the online communication and dissemination and to be considered as one of the main channels that will be used to increase project's visibility and impact towards all relevant stakeholders.

The website provides to the audience valuable information on the project's goals and assets, the partners, the proposed activities and the foreseen results. It also provides links to the project's social media accounts - Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn, in every page, and motivated via the "Get involved" menu, interactivity between the partners and the interested parties. Interactivity and updated content will attract the attention for repeated visits.

More information about each section will be presented in more details in the chapters below accompanied with the respective screenshots from the official website.

The website platform is easy to use, fast, and informative, used for the dissemination of deliverables, open access publications, presentations, newsletters etc. It also includes information about the project and offers the option for the stakeholders interested in our activities, to contact the project partners. Interested parties are able to register and receive updated information and in parallel identify opportunities for partnerships, joint ventures etc.

In order to maximize its visibility, free or affordable methods to increase page ranking on search engines may be used.

The website will continue to be updated as the project progresses.

1.2 Website Access

The site's core is based on Word press 7. The website during the first stages of its development was hosted under the URLs: <https://temp.hyperion-project.eu/> and <https://hyperion.zulupixels.com/>

The website, being a dissemination tool, is also presented in the social media accounts of the HYPERION project to increase the dissemination impact providing further and more in depth information about project.

1.2.1 Responsibilities and Roles

The HYPERION project team as an entity is responsible for ensuring that all content is relevant and up to date. All project partners, are responsible to provide in time the results and information about the activities they carried out, as well as any news, to the WP9 leader.

Each partner is responsible for the integrity of the information they provide to IEMC and ICCS.

The consortium, as a whole, is responsible for delivering updates to be uploaded in the HYPERION's project website.

IEMC technical staff, the webmaster Konstantinos Gkanetsos, will proactively act to ensure that the latest information is available on the website, being responsible for the website update.

The structure of the website and all its elements must be approved by the Project Management Board (PMB) and the Project Coordinator (PC).

1.3 Hosting and maintenance

The site is hosted by ICCS.

Technical Maintenance: IEMC is responsible for the technical maintenance of the website. In case of any question or difficulty regarding technical maintenance, Mr. Konstantinos Gkanetsos is the contact point from the consortium.

An external website developer was responsible for the website development in cooperation with the IEMC and will support all technical issues, if anything arises, during the project life (i.e. and five years after the end of the project).

1.4 Site components

The website provides all relevant information about HYPERION. The homepage contains 8 parts (menus) as follows:

- ABOUT
- PARTNERS
- TEST SITES
- RESULTS TO DATE
- NEWSROOM
- GET INVOLVED
- LIAISONS
- CONTACT US

In the footnote of every page the disclaimer, and the website's designer link are included.

2. WEBSITE CONTENT

2.1 Homepage

HomePage Access and structure: Entering the url mentioned previously, the user will be directed to the home page. Writing to any search engine "Hyperion eu", the first among 5.370K results, is the project's home page.

This page consists of the navigation menu, a slider and the options "See more", "Stay informed", and "Read about our test sites".

The user can also be redirected to the Home Page by simply clicking the Hyperion logo, which is pinned at the upper part at every page of our website.

The navigation main menu links the Home Page and the rest of the pages, divided in 8 submenus with the relevant content.

2.1.1 Stay informed

Through this button, visitors will have the opportunity to stay informed about the project by registering in the HYPERION subscription list to receive the project's upcoming news (newsletters, annual magazine, invitations about HYPERION's future events and workshops, etc.).

Regarding the subscriptions to project news, interested visitors could subscribe by simply entering a few details on an online form provided. This form can be founded on

the Home Page and also in the Newsletter page. Every time a new user fills the form an e-mail is sent to sophia.adam@iccs.gr and to gkanetsos@iemcunesco.org as a notification. At the same time a notification email is sent to the subscriber.

Registration forms are harmonized to the EU General Data Protection Legislation (GDPR) issues and the relevant procedures are committed to protecting and respecting subscribers' privacy.

Figure 1: The HYPERION project homepage

2.2 About

This is the first submenu, as the user navigates from the left to the right. It redirects the user to the following six pages which provide basic information about the Hyperion program. The pages' titles included in this section being on display are:

- The HYPERION project Vision,

- The concept,
- Objectives,
- To whom it may concern,
- Impact and
- innovation potential

Figure 2: Screenshot from the Impact submenu of the “ABOUT” section

Figure 3: Screenshot from the Concept submenu of the “ABOUT” section

2.3 Partners

In this section the logo and the abbreviated name of each organisation are displayed. By clicking on the abbreviated name, the user can access data about the partner organisation and also may access partner’s website from the link which is provided. The page also includes a map with the participant’s exact location. It was built with the WP Google Maps plugin. All the images and information used in these pages, were provided by the partners and are uploaded at the REDMINE internal communication tool.

Figure 4: Partial View from the “Partners” Section

2.4 Test Sites

Information and visual material for all four sites are included in this section. When the user places the mouse over the site under examination, it is twisted and then by clicking on “MORE” the user gets information about the site as well visual info about it. The available infrastructure is also provided. Placing the mouse over the icon the user can zoom in it.

Figure 5: View from the “test sites” homepage

2.5 Results to date

Deliverables, publications and presentations are included in this section. All existing public results will be uploaded, following all the steps which are included in the procedures of the HYPERION program. This is a downloadable area where every individual can find information about the project in depth.

2.6 Newsroom

This submenu navigates the user to five different pages. All of them refer to the latest news regarding HYPERION. The following topics are listed:

News: It is the attracting part of newsroom, and will constantly be updated with information about the project activities and results throughout the entire lifetime of the project. Currently, it includes content and photos from the first programme meeting in Rhodes and information about the sensors installation with photos from Tonsberg. By clicking on the photo you get the enlarged version. All pictures are shareable via Facebook, Twitter, Reddit, Digg and Delicious. It may also include related European news and events (updated by the HYPERION project team with partners' assistance when relevant).

The screenshot shows the Hyperion project website's newsroom section. At the top, the Hyperion logo is centered. Below it is a navigation menu with items: About, Partners, Test Sites, Results to date, Newsroom (highlighted), Get Involved, Liaisons, and Contact us. A large green banner with the word "News" is positioned below the menu. Two news items are displayed in a grid:

- 1st Programme Meeting of Hyperion Project in Rhodes**
Below you can find pictures from the first HYPERION programme [...]
- Visit to Slottsfjelet museum**
In the framework of Hyperion project, research groups from Oslo [...]

At the bottom, a green banner features the European Union flag on the left and the following text on the right:

- A 4-year EC Funded project
- Start date: 1st of June, 2019
- HYPERION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 821054.

Figure 6: View from the “News” submenu of the newsroom section

Newsletter: In this section, all newsletters issued within the lifetime of the project will be available to see. Visitors that wish, might also subscribe and join HYPERION news of project activities and developments, outputs and events.

Magazines: In this section, visitors could find the HYPERION annual magazine issues and those who wish, might also subscribe to next ones.

In the Media: In this section press releases, press clippings and relevant press articles will be available to see and share. (Fig. 7)

Figure 7: View from “In the Media” submenu

Media Kit: In this section, visitors could find and download HYPERION’s produced communication material. (Fig. 8)

Figure 8: View from “Media Kit” submenu

2.7 Get Involved

Each visitor of HYPERION website will have the opportunity to get involved to the project in various ways, such as registering in the HYPERION subscription list to receive the project's upcoming news (newsletters, annual magazine, invitations about HYPERION's future events and workshops, etc.), following the project on social media, participating in surveys, interviews and workshops and also providing their feedback via email.

Figure 9: Screenshot from the “Get Involved” menu

2.8 Liaisons

Figure 10: Partial screenshot from the “Liaisons” menu

HYPERION will collaborate with European Research and Technological Development initiatives, participating in important working groups and events. Networking, co-organising sessions in EU conferences and preparation of joint dissemination activities, will be included in this section. EU programs of similar content are presented.

2.9 Contact Us

Direct contact to the main persons involved in the project (the project coordinator, the project manager, the dissemination manager, the website maintainer) is provided through this page. Using the e-mailing option the visitor can directly communicate with the persons mentioned above.

The screenshot shows a 'Contact us' page with a green header. Below the header, it asks 'Do you want to learn more about HYPERION?' and provides a link to subscribe to newsletters and magazines. The main content is titled 'Project Contact Details' and is divided into two sections: 'For Technical enquiries' and 'For Media or Communications enquiries'.

For Technical enquiries

Dr Angelos Amditis	Dr. Antonis Kalis
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For Media or Communications enquiries

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+30-210-772-2526		

Figure 11: The “Contact us” page

3. TECHNICAL DATA

Theme: The theme selected for the website is Avada Child. The choice was made in order to have access to all the plugins necessary and have the best possible visual result.

Software: The website was developed using Wordpress, which is an open source software tool platform and offers various plugins. The domain necessary was provided

by the ICCS.

Letter Size: In the main menu the size of the letters used were 18px and 15px for the submenus. For the Social Media Icons & copyright section the letter size is 15px.

For Hyperion’s Vision, Objectives, To whom it may concern the letter size used is 18px.

Impact: A pop modal with the content appears. This was used to solve the problem of scrolling down and the difficulty we had because of the different size of the used documents which should be aligned.

Slider: The slider was made using the Slider Revolution 6 plugin of the Wordpress platform. The pictures used in the slide show have been carefully selected to cover test sites of the HYPERION Project, immediately referring to them.

Images: All the images used on this website were either taken, or selected by our partners.

3.1 Plugins

The plugins used for this website are presented in the following table 1.

Table 1. List of used plugins

Name of the used Plugin
Contact Form 7
Duplicate Post
Duplicator
Fusion Builder
Fusion Core
MC4WP (Mailchimp for Word Press)
Nifty Coming Soon & Maintenance page
Page Visit Counter
Post Type Switcher
Slider Revolution
WP Google Maps
The events Calendar
Yoast SEO
Avada Multi purpose Theme

3.2 Widgets

The following widgets were added to the website:

Twitter widget: A Twitter widget displaying 3-5 of the most recent tweets, also providing a link to our Twitter profile to ease people to follow us. The widget will pull information from our Twitter account and updates the feed to the widget in real time.

Facebook widget: Coding-free Facebook Feed widget for website will be used.

Events: A calendar with brief description and data about the upcoming events that HYPERION’s members may attend is included. From each one of them the user can navigate to the next event, appearing in chronological order, which can be found in the bottom of the page.

The screenshot displays a website event page for the 'Hyperion Plenary Meeting' held from April 22 to April 24. The main heading is 'Hyperion Plenary Meeting April 22 - April 24'. Below this is the Hyperion logo and a text block stating: 'Next Plenary meeting of Hyperion EU Programme will be held in Granada from 22 to 24 April 2020.' It also shows 'Total Page Visits: 7 - Today Page Visits: 5'. There are two buttons: '+ GOOGLE CALENDAR' and '+ I CAL EXPORT'. Social media icons for Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Pinterest are present. A 'Details' sidebar on the right shows the start and end dates. At the bottom, there is a link: 'Adapt Northern Heritage Conference >'

Figure 12: “Events” page

3.3 Website Maintenance

Development, maintenance and content update for the HYPERION project website is done by IEMC under the supervision of ICCS.

This includes uploading of the public deliverables as well as announcements of information and events to be displayed online.

3.4 Statistics

For the better assessment of the site's progress and the reaction of the readers to our posts/news the Page Visit Counter plugin is used.

The administrator is collecting the statistical data provided through Google Analytics (i.e. number of sessions, unique visitors, number of pages visited, etc.).

3.5 Cookies policy

The website follows the Commission's guidelines on privacy and data protection and inform users that cookies are not being used to gather information unnecessarily. The ePrivacy directive – more specifically Article 5(3) – requires prior informed consent for storage or for access to information stored on a user's terminal equipment.

3.6 Disclaimer

HYPERION website includes the following disclaimer.

HYPERION project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 821054.

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This website is maintained by:

IEMC UNESCO, (Mr. Konstantinos Gkanetsos)

Design, Concept, editing

IEMC UNESCO (K.Gkanetsos, P.Yannakopoulos, K.Zountouridis, S.Adam)

Programming and web content management system

IEMC UNESCO (Mr. Konstantinos Gkanetsos)

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4. CONCLUSION

HYPERION website is the main online channel to present the project's vision, developments and ongoing activities and also disseminate all the results and outputs to relevant audiences and stakeholders. The website has been built so as to be attractive and interesting to both experts and non-experts visitors and aims to provide a concise overview of all the latest technological developments in the HYPERION's fields. Moreover, the website has been designed in consistency with the already produced brand identity of the project.

Regarding the content including, the website contains all information regarding the HYPERION concept, objectives, consortium, contact details, public documents etc. serving all purposes of WP9, and specifically the diffusion of project's achievements and results to its interested stakeholders, the general public and the experts network.

It is a live website which means that it will be frequently updated so as to keep the visitors updated with the latest news and activities, latest information and public documents of the project. In addition, all contact details will be available for all interested parties to keep in touch with the project consortium.

5. REFERENCES

<https://theme-fusion.com/documentation/avada/install-update/avada-child-theme>

6. ANNEXES

Annex 1: Website screenshots

In this annex selected pages from the website are presented

Selected Screenshots from the Website

f t in

About ▾ Partners Test Sites Results to date ▾ Newsroom ▾ Get Involved Liaisons Contact us

NSB 2020

NSB 2020 June 14 - June 17

The 12 Nordic Symposium on building Physics will be held in Tallin at 14-17 June
More info : <https://nsb2020.org/>

Total Page Visits: 14 - Today Page Visits: 1

+ GOOGLE CALENDAR + ICAL EXPORT

f t in d

< Adapt Northern Heritage Conference World Conference on Earthquake engineering >

Details

Start:
June 14

End:
June 17

Website:
<https://nsb2020.org/>

Privacy & Cookies Policy

Hyperion

The Concept

Hyperion offers an overarching strategy that includes risk management, protection and preservation as complementary strategies to prevent damage to cultural sites, identify and ease off additional threats and promote adaptation, restoration and other post-damage strategies to return normal conditions to the historic area, as well as long-term strategic approaches to adapt to climate change and to meet policy goals for economic, cultural, and environmental objectives.

Hyperion will introduce a research framework for downscaling the created climate and atmospheric composition as well as associated risk maps down to the 1m scale. Applying atmospheric modelling for specific climate change scenarios at such refined spatial and time scales allows for an accurate quantitative and qualitative impact assessment of the estimated micro-climatic and atmospheric changes.

Hyperion will perform combined Hydro-Thermal and Structural-Gasotechnical analysis of the Cultural Heritage sites and damage assessment (under normal (past) and changed (future) conditions (atmospheric and natural conditions), based on the climate data, the micro-climate conditions, the morphologic and physical-mechanical features of existing materials, historic data for the structures, the effect of previous hydrological processes and the environmental/climatic characteristics of the surrounding environment). The data coming from the deployed sensors will be coupled with simulated data over the wider Cultural Heritage area (under realistic real assessment Platform) and will be further analysed through our data management system and expert assessment/ participation and public awareness. The data from the sensors will feed the Decision Support System to provide appropriate adaptation and mitigation strategies, and support sustainable, reconstruction plans for the cultural heritage (damage to the remaining assets).

The Hyperion system sets up to an advanced visualization tool with improved 4D capabilities (3D plus time) that can provide a simple and easy way for all relevant stakeholders to assess heritage and risk. The enhanced visualization tool (based on the produced climate risk regional models) will be used by the local authorities to assess the threats of climate change and other natural hazards, visualize the built heritage and cultural services under future climate scenarios, model the effects of different adaptation strategies, and ultimately prioritize any rehabilitation actions to lead allocated funds to both pre- and post-event environments.

A 4-year EC funded project
Start date: 1st of June, 2019
Hyperion has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821054.

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The screenshot shows the Hyperion project website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the following items: About, Partners, Test Sites, Results to date, Newsroom, Get involved, Links, and Contact us. Below the navigation bar is a large green banner with the text "Innovation Potential".

The main content area is titled "Three pillars of innovation are included in HYPERION". It lists three key areas of innovation:

- Material-specific dose-response equations for increasing dynamic Heat-Air-Moisture models accuracy:** HYPERION will fill the gap of inadequacy of dose-response deterioration equations and lack in considering site-specific environmental parameters influencing future climate conditions, by improving the knowledge on measurable parameters influencing degradation rates, and refining adequate material-specific recession models to be integrated in vulnerability simulations under high-resolution site-optimized climate projections.
- Modelling tools and simulators to be used for increasing the resilience of the historic areas:** HYPERION will identify an optimal set of quantitative primary parameters and impact indicators to quantify climate change impacts on cultural heritage, encompassing climate extremes, hydrological and soil quality, and structural stress indicators. Parameter selection will consider the probability distributions of mean temperature and diurnal variation, surface hygrometry, CO₂ concentrations as well as pressure inputs for wind. Uncertainties of environmental model inputs and material parameters will be quantified by uncertainty models, based on these sources.
- Multi-scale and multi-reading approaches for the assessment of atmospheric forcing on soil and structures:** New multi-scale and multi-reading approaches for the assessment of atmospheric forcing on soil and structures will be developed to help determine the soil temperature and moisture content for different scenarios. The relevant environmental stresses related to the selected infrastructures under different climate scenarios and the evaluation of the efficiency of response actions will be identified.

Additional text on the page includes:

- Downscaling of high-resolution regional climate model will be performed at computational grids with horizontal resolution of a few km (0.5-2 km) in the targeted areas for specific episodes with high-impact weather and climate events. The selection of the events will be based on climate data in a way so that extreme events can be simulated and assessed.
- The integration of monitoring data from advanced sensors along with the experts' knowledge will allow for improved system identification and consequently more accurate vulnerability assessment. The availability of various scenarios stemming from high-resolution regional climate model as well as multiple sources of monitoring data to be exploited by the Structural/Deterioration simulator will allow for a more accurate prediction of the structural safety risk due to future climate change for existing structures. This will be extended to modern materials.
- Modeling the function dose-response is crucial for understanding the behaviour of old materials that are not included in available databases. The range of materials and construction assemblies, as well as the variation of material periods that the cultural heritage sites included in HYPERION were built, will allow the creation of a materials database suitable for heat-air-moisture simulations of heritage buildings and constructions. Furthermore, the HYPERION Hydro-Thermal simulator tool will include climate scenarios based on various well-documented climate change models to predict Hydro-Thermal performance of building construction elements and materials degradation under these conditions.
- The open-source/architecture of Historic Risk Assessment Platform will enable an unprecedented increase in the number of available models, data, and network simulators to flow between end-users, engineers, catalytic risk modellers, and stakeholders. Standardisation and openness will allow a vibrant community to build around it, embracing existing open-source or free software and allowing inter-connectivity with proprietary simulators via standardised Application Programming Interfaces.

Hyperion

About Partners **Test Sites** Results to Date Newsroom Get Involved Licenses Contact us

Test Sites

HYPERION will perform extensive tests in four demo sites, in Greece (Rodos), Spain (Granada), Norway (Trondheim), and Italy (Venezia). The historic areas will be modelled at building level through reduced-order models based on archetype structures of each area. A number of selected structures (DR value) will be modelled and monitored in detail. The demonstration shall prove the suitability of the HYPERION platform for multiple hazard assessment and optimized operational and strategic decisions for management and maintenance of the historic areas, considering as well other hazards relevant for other sections of the city.

- Værfold og Telemark Fylkeskommune (VTFK)
- Comune di Venezia (CVT)
- Dimos Rodos (DR) and Ephorate of Antiquities of the Dodecanese (EFAD)
- Ayuntamiento De Granada (ADG)

© 4-year EC Funded project
Start date: 1st of June, 2019
HYPERION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 821054.

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The screenshot shows the 'In The Media' section of the Hyperion project website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Hyperion logo and menu items: About, Partners, Test Sites, Results to date, **Newsroom**, Get Involved, Liaisons, and Contact us. Below the navigation bar is a green header with the text 'In The Media'. The main content area is white and features the heading 'Welcome HYPERION presence in the Media!' followed by social media icons for Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn. The section is titled 'Hyperion press Clippings' and includes a sub-heading 'In this section you might find HYPERION's favorite Press Clippings. Enjoy reading!'. There are seven press clipping entries, each with a title in Greek, a source link, and a 'Read more' button. The entries are: 1. 'HYPERION: Ο Στρατός, νησικός «αντιτηρή»' (26/06/2019); 2. 'HYPERION: THE European Digital Conservator' (26/06/2019); 3. 'HYPERION: Ο Στρατός, νησικός «αντιτηρή» των μεγάλων εκπομπών κλιματικής' (27/06/2019); 4. 'HYPERION: Ο ΣΥΓΧΡΑΤΟΣ ΠΗΛΑΙΟΣ ΣΥΝΤΗΡΗΣΗ ΤΩΝ ΑΡΧΑΙΟΛΟΓΙΚΩΝ ΣΤΟΙΧΩΝ ΚΑΙ ΤΩΝ ΜΟΡΦΩΣΕΩΝ ΠΟΛΙΤΙΣΤΙΚΗΣ ΚΑΙΡΟΠΟΙΗΣΑΣ' (27/06/2019); 5. 'HYPERION: Ο Στρατός, νησικός «αντιτηρή» των αρχαιολογικών χώρων και των μεγάλων εκπομπών κλιματικής – Μιλτιάδης Αβραμίου, κριτικός λόγος για τη διατήρηση των εκπομπών κλιματικής' (27/06/2019); 6. 'HYPERION: Ο Στρατός, νησικός «αντιτηρή» των μεγάλων εκπομπών κλιματικής – Μιλτιάδης Αβραμίου, κριτικός λόγος για τη διατήρηση των εκπομπών κλιματικής' (27/06/2019); 7. 'HYPERION: Ο Στρατός, νησικός «αντιτηρή» των αρχαιολογικών χώρων και των μεγάλων εκπομπών κλιματικής – Μιλτιάδης Αβραμίου, κριτικός λόγος για τη διατήρηση των εκπομπών κλιματικής' (26/06/2019). The final entry is 'Είτε, νησικός «αντιτηρή» αρχαιολογικών χώρων και μεγάλων εκπομπών κλιματικής από το ΕΜΕΓ' (25/06/2019). At the bottom of the page, there is a green footer containing the European Union flag, the text 'A 4-year EC Funded project', 'Start date: Tet of June, 2019', 'HYPERION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 821054', and a 'Privacy & Cookies Policy' link.

The screenshot shows the 'In The Media' section of the Hyperion project website. At the top, there is a dark brown navigation bar with social media icons for Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn. Below this is the Hyperion logo and a horizontal menu with items: About, Partners, Test Sites, Results to date, Newsroom (highlighted), Get involved, Liaisons, and Contact us. The main heading 'In The Media' is centered in a light green banner. Below the heading, a message reads 'Welcome HYPERION presence in the Media!' followed by social media icons for Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn. The section is titled 'Hyperion press Clippings' with a subtext: 'In this section you might find HYPERION's favorite Press Clippings. Enjoy reading!'. Below this, there is a placeholder for a press clipping with fields for 'TITLE OF PRESS CLIPPING', 'SOURCE LINK | DATE | Read more'. A light green banner at the bottom features the European Union flag on the left and text on the right: 'A 4-year EC Funded project', 'Start date: 1st of June, 2019', and 'HYPERION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 821054'. The footer contains copyright information: '© Copyright 2018 | Hyperion-Project | All Rights Reserved | Designed by subpixels.com | Disclaimer' and social media icons for Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn.

- About ▾
- Partners
- Test Sites
- Results to date ▾
- Newsroom ▾
- Get Involved
- Liaisons
- Contact us

Newsletter

First name or full name

Email

Subscribe

Total Page Visits: 20 - Today Page Visits: 1

A 4-year EC Funded project

Start date: 1st of June, 2019

HYPERION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 821054.

The screenshot displays the Hyperion project website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Hyperion logo and links for 'About', 'Partners', 'Next Steps', 'Results to Date', 'Newsroom', 'Get Involved', 'Locations', and 'Contact us'. Below this is a prominent yellow 'Get Involved' section. It features two main options: 'Newsletter' and 'In the media'. The 'Newsletter' option includes the text: 'Register to our newsletter. This way you'll get information on future events, projects, activities and developments, courses and events. This can be done simply via subscribing on our mailing list.' The 'In the media' option includes the text: 'Feature us on social media. You can feature HYPERION on the following social media.' Below these options is a vertical feed of social media posts from the 'Hyperion EU Project' account. Further down is a dark green 'Stay Informed!' section with a 'Subscribe here!' button. Below that, a yellow banner contains the text: 'A 4-year EU Funded project. Start date: July of June, 2014. HYPERION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821054.' The footer includes the text: '© Hyperion EU | Hyperion.eu | All Rights Reserved | European Commission | Disclaimer' and three social media icons.

The screenshot displays the 'Hyperion' project website. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for 'About', 'Partners', 'Test Sites', 'Results to date', 'Newsroom', 'Get involved', 'Literature', and 'Contact us'. Below this is a green banner with the heading 'Liasons'. The main content area features a list of project partners, each with a logo and a brief description:

- PLUGGY**: PLUGGY addresses the need of the society to be actively involved in cultural heritage activities, not only as an observer, but also as a participant, creator and a manager. [Read More](#)
- ARCH**: ARCH is a European-funded research project that aims to better preserve areas of cultural heritage from habitats and risks. The ARCH team with the office of Balthazar. [Read More](#)
- Shelter**: SHELTER aims at developing a data driven and community based knowledge framework that will bring together the scientific, community and heritage managers with the objective. [Read More](#)
- STORM**: Starting from previous research experiences and tangible outcomes, STORM proposes a set of novel predictive models and improved normative and non-destructive methods. [Read More](#)
- HERACLES**: HERACLES project is to propose a holistic, multidisciplinary and multi-stakeholder approach with the aim to provide an operative system and contributions to innovate and. [Read More](#)

At the bottom of the page, there is a green banner with the European Union flag logo and the text: 'A year EC funded project. Start date: 1st of June, 2019. HYPERION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 821054.' Below this banner is a footer with copyright information: '© Copyright 2019 | HyperionProject | All Rights Reserved | Designed by gubbi.com | Barcelona' and social media icons.

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Hyperion

About - Partners Test Sites Results to date - Newroom - Get Involved Liaisons **Contact us**

Contact us

Do you want to learn more about HYPERION?
Don't hesitate to reach us through the contacts below or subscribe to our newsletter and annual magazines [here!](#)

Project Contact Details

For Technical enquiries

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For Media or Communications enquiries

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 A 4-year EC Funded project
Start date: 1st of June, 2019
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